

Ancient Egypt - Predynastic Period - Early Naqada Culture

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Entry tags: Egyptian Religions, Prehistoric Religion, African Religions, Religious Group

The early Naqada culture of Upper Egypt (in the south), refers to the cultural assemblage found in this area of Egypt during the Predynastic Period. This is what Egyptologists refer to as Naqada I-IIIb, approximately 4000-2950 BCE (though these dates are somewhat debated). Most of this period is devoid of texts, with simple labels showing up right at the end. This means that our religious knowledge for this era is completely based on an interpretation of the material evidence. Many of these interpretations are built on the belief of continuity of practice between this early phase and later Egyptian religion. This is somewhat problematic, as the meaning of objects and practices may have changed over time. There is therefore disagreement on what religion was like in this prehistoric period, which should be kept in mind. As new evidence surfaces, these interpretations may change. For the moment, Egyptologists generally see the Naqada culture as the foundation of what we currently understand to be ancient Egyptian religion. Many of the iconic images of pharaonic power and religion are first seen at this time, and continue to be used for thousands of years. The practices of the Naqada culture people began in the south of Egypt, but during this period they spread north, and replace the Buto-Maadi culture. This is therefore a crucial period in the history of ancient Egyptian religion.

Date Range: 4000 BCE - 2950 BCE

Region: Peregrine_UpperEgyptPreDynastic

Region tags: Africa, Egypt

From Peter N. Peregrine's Encyclopedia of Prehistory.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Andelkovic, Branislav 2011. "Political Organization of Egypt in the Predynastic Period" in *Before the Pyramids: the Origins of Egyptian Civilization*, edited by Emily Teeter. Oriental Institute Museum Publications 33. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, pp. 25-32.
- Source 2: Wengrow, David 2006. *The Archaeology of Early Egypt: Social Transformations in North-East Africa, 10,000-2650 BC*. Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Source 3: Teeter, Emily (editor) 2011. *Before the Pyramids: the Origins of Egyptian Civilization*. Oriental Institute Museum Publications 33. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago.

Reference: D. Wengrow. *The Archaeology of Early Egypt*. Cambridge University Press. isbn: 9780521835862.

Reference: University of Chicago. Oriental Institute. Museum, Emily Teeter. *Before the Pyramids*. Oriental Inst Publications Sales. isbn: 9781885923820.

– Source 1: Hendrickx, Stan 2011. "Iconography of the Predynastic and Early Dynastic Periods" in *Before the Pyramids: the Origins of Egyptian Civilization*, edited by Emily Teeter. Oriental Institute Museum Publications 33. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, pp. 75-82.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://uee.cdh.ucla.edu/articles/predynastic_burials

– Source 1 Description: Article on Predynastic Burials by Alice Stevenson from the UCLA Encyclopedia of Egyptology.

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.metmuseum.org/toah/keywords/predynastic-period-in-egypt/>

– Source 1 Description: Metropolitan Museum - Heilbrunn Timeline of Art History

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The two main groups within Egypt during the Predynastic Period (roughly the 4th millennium BCE) are referred to as the Naqada culture in Upper Egypt and the Buto-Maadi culture in Lower Egypt, based on the material culture found at the type sites. In the later predynastic (referred to as Naqada IIc) the cultural complex of Upper Egypt began to replace that in Lower Egypt, eventually becoming dominant. What caused the spread, whether a slow preference in styles or beliefs, social dominance of the Upper Egyptian peoples, or perhaps warfare, is debated. War was once the monocausal explanation for this cultural replacement, based in part on the images seen in the Narmer palette. This is now considered outdated, and most scholars lean towards a more complicated, multi-causal acculturation process.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The two main groups within Egypt during the Predynastic Period (roughly the 4th millennium BCE) are referred to as the Naqada culture in Upper Egypt and the Buto-Maadi culture in Lower Egypt, based on the material culture found at the type sites. In the later predynastic (referred to as Naqada IIc) the cultural complex of Upper Egypt, began to replace that in Lower Egypt, eventually becoming dominant. What caused the spread, whether a slow preference in styles or beliefs, social dominance of the Upper Egyptian peoples, or perhaps warfare, is debated. War was once the monocausal explanation for this cultural replacement, based in part on the images seen in the Narmer palette. This is now considered outdated, and most scholars lean towards a more complicated, multi-causal acculturation process.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The two main groups within Egypt during the Predynastic Period (roughly the 4th millennium BCE) are referred to as the Naqada culture in Upper Egypt and the Buto-Maadi culture in Lower Egypt, based on the material culture found at the type sites. In the later

predynastic (referred to as Naqada IIc) the cultural complex of Upper Egypt, began to replace that in Lower Egypt, eventually becoming dominant. What caused the spread, whether a slow preference in styles or beliefs, social dominance of the Upper Egyptian peoples, or perhaps warfare, is debated. War was once the monocausal explanation for this cultural replacement, based in part on the images seen in the Narmer palette. This is now considered outdated, and most scholars lean towards a more complicated, multi-causal acculturation process.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The two main groups within Egypt during the Predynastic Period (roughly the 4th millennium BCE) are referred to as the Naqada culture in Upper Egypt and the Buto-Maadi culture in Lower Egypt, based on the material culture found at the type sites. In the later predynastic (referred to as Naqada IIc) the cultural complex of Upper Egypt, began to replace that in Lower Egypt, eventually becoming dominant. What caused the spread, whether a slow preference in styles or beliefs, social dominance of the Upper Egyptian peoples, or perhaps warfare, is debated. War was once the monocausal explanation for this cultural replacement, based in part on the images seen in the Narmer palette. This is now considered outdated, and most scholars lean towards a more complicated, multi-causal acculturation process.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Within this period, images of smiting and taking captives are visible in the iconography. There is little physical evidence of warfare, however. Some violence between the people of Upper and Lower Egypt is assumed due to landscape references such as those on the Narmer Palette. Whether there was also fighting within the separate cultures is unclear, though the eventual dominance of select areas has been interpreted by some scholars to suggest an expansion that may have been violent.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The two main groups within Egypt during the Predynastic Period (roughly the 4th millennium BCE) are referred to as the Naqada culture in Upper Egypt and the Buto-Maadi culture in Lower Egypt, based on the material culture found at the type sites. In the later predynastic (referred to as Naqada IIc) the cultural complex of Upper Egypt, began to replace that in Lower Egypt, eventually becoming dominant. What caused the spread, whether a slow preference in styles or beliefs, social dominance of the Upper Egyptian peoples, or perhaps warfare, is debated. War was once the monocausal explanation for this cultural replacement, based in part on the images seen in the Narmer palette. This is now considered outdated, and most scholars lean towards a more complicated, multi-causal acculturation process.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: There are no textual references from this period, so we cannot be certain; however, it looks like belief in the gods was assumed, rather than debated. To be Egyptian was to believe in the Egyptian gods, and partake in their worship.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: There are no textual references from this period, so we cannot be certain; however, it looks like belief in the gods was assumed, rather than debated. To be Egyptian was to believe in the Egyptian gods, and partake in their worship.

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to say during this early period. At this time, Egypt was just becoming socially stratified. Only at the later end do we see individuals who seem to be local leaders who are able to support the religion.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Religious practice slowly builds during this period to create customs that would continue for millennia. These practices would, however, replace those in the north.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Over 15,000 burials have been found dating to the predynastic period in Upper Egypt. This is the only means of estimating the population, but is unreliable, as only a few sites have been identified, and it is likely that many of the burials have been destroyed due to their age and later habitations.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: This is a prehistoric period - there are no texts.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: It is somewhat debated whether the architectural remains at Hierakonpolis should be called "monumental", but there is evidence for a large ceremonial center at this site (referred to as HK29A). Here there is a large oval courtyard with a gateway, and significant evidence of butchering and subsequent animal burials (see Friedman 2011).

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little remaining evidence from this period to answer.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little remaining evidence from this period to answer.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little remaining evidence from this period to answer.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little remaining evidence from this period to answer.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little remaining evidence from this period to answer.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little remaining evidence from this period to answer.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: The only (debatable) evidence for monumental architecture comes from Hierakonpolis (Friedman 2011).

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of iconography from this period comes from burial contexts. Images of ships, captives, figures in a "smiting" pose, and taming of wild animals include some of the most common motifs.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: There were clearly large religious spaces such as those found at Hierakonpolis. The main areas of religious iconography that survive from this period, however, were decorated tombs and funerary objects.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Images of curved ships with oars, and the mastery of different wild animals are common motifs.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Eyes tend to be shown large and round.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Animals with enhanced features - particularly "serpopards": leopards depicted with serpentine necks. Bulls and horned cows also appear, which may be representative of the divine power of a king to control chaos.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: It is a bit ambiguous whether the human figures depicted in tombs from this period are supernatural or human, though it is generally believed that there was already a belief in a divine ruler who was able to control chaos in this early period. This is seen as early as Naqada Ia on pottery from Abydos tomb U329, where an image of a man with horns, a bull tail, and a mace can be seen - an early version of the "smiting scene". This is then carried onto the walls of Hierakonpolis tomb 100, where a lion-tamer image is also visible.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: Emblems that are later symbols for various gods have been found from this period. Some of these take the form of standards depicted on pottery (Teeter 2011:174). An emblem of the goddess Bat, for instance, was found in tomb 16 at the cemetery HK6 in Hierakonpolis (Friedman 2011:38-39).

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In some tombs, such as tomb 100 in Hierakonpolis, there are images of the "lion-tamer", ships, captured peoples being controlled, and more. It is unclear whether these images record only instances of daily life, or if they might refer to the afterlife. In later periods, such scenes do seem to show an idealized life after death.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Humans are frequently depicted dancing, or fighting. An image of a male fighting lions, the "lion tamer" is a recurring motif as well.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Boats take on a significant importance within iconography in tombs and on objects. This may be in relation to movement along the Nile in daily life, or may be a reference to the journey to the afterlife, which they acquire in later periods.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Hierakonpolis seems to be a particularly sacred site and ceremonial center, built up over a long period of time (Friedman 2011).

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: There is little evidence from this period, but all religious sites in Egypt (all sites in general, for that matter) were by the river Nile. Large rock outcroppings and raised areas seem to have been particularly popular for all eras.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence for this during this period, but there are long distance trade routes, and the frequent depiction of boats suggest that they were an important feature.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Although there is little evidence from this period to provide details, the intricate burials suggest that the inhabitants believed in an afterlife where elements of the soul could carry on a new existence. In later Egyptian history, this developed into a complicated conception of the body and different elements of the soul or personality (the 'ba' and 'ka') that combined to create an individual's identity.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The elaborate burials suggest a belief in the afterlife at this time. Due to a lack of textual information, however, it is difficult to be clear on the details of their beliefs.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Although there is little evidence from this period to provide details, the intricate burials suggest that the inhabitants believed in an afterlife where elements of the soul could carry on a new existence. In later Egyptian history, this developed into a complicated conception of the body and different elements of the soul or personality that combined to create an individual's identity.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Although there is little evidence from this period to provide details, the intricate burials suggest that the inhabitants believed in an afterlife where elements of the soul could carry on a new existence.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to suggest details about afterlife beliefs for this period.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: In this period, after death bodies were generally laid in sandy pits, where their bodies would dry out and often preserve naturally. They were buried with funerary objects, often pieces like combs or beads, palettes, or pottery. Towards the end of this period, as social stratification became more pronounced, tombs and offerings became more elaborate. Tomb U-j at Abydos for instance, contained many works of art and jugs of wine. Mummification is certainly not common during this period, but there is evidence from Hierakonpolis (Naqada IIA-B) for what seems to be an early form of this practice (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: Mummification is certainly not common during this period, but there is evidence from Hierakonpolis (Naqada IIA-B) for what seems to be an early form of this practice (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: During the Naqada period, burials usually took the form of single, rectangular burials. These range from simple pit burials where the body is wrapped in a mat, to more substantial burials consisting of multiple rooms with considerable grave goods for the elite (see Stevenson 2009).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: For most of the burials from this period, the bodies are contracted (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: Usually the corpse is contracted, but there were a few exceptions.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Occasionally, the body has been found in secondary burials, either in ceramic pots, or with the bones reorganized (Stevenson 2009; Wengrow 2006).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: The dry desert often caused natural mummification, but even with secondary burials, the body seems to have been buried, not left exposed.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Some references to "post-interment removal of the skull" (Stevenson 2009:4; Midant-Reynes et al. 1996:90), and rearrangement of the bones after initial burial (Wengrow 2006:116-119).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: Some references to "post-interment removal of the skull" (Stevenson 2009:4; Midant-Reynes et al. 1996:90), and rearrangement of the bones after initial burial (Wengrow 2006:116-119).

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Well this generally does not seem to be the case for this period, there are subsidiary graves connected to tomb 16 at the elite cemetery at HK6 in Hierakonpolis. It is unclear whether this might be evidence of sacrifice (see Friedman 2011:39).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: For most of this period, pottery is a significant burial object. Other items like beads, pins, combs, blades and bladelets can be found also. Towards the end of the period, as stratification becomes wider, there are more objects that represent a greater amount of wealth - in the tomb of U-j at Abydos, for instance, there were imported objects made of Lebanese cedar and obsidian.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Spoons, beads, pins, combs, remnants of clothing, figurines, blades and bladelets, and ceramics are found relatively commonly in Naqada burials (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Towards the end of the period, as stratification becomes wider, there are more objects that represent a greater amount of wealth - in the tomb of U-j at Abydos, for instance, there were imported objects made of Lebanese cedar and obsidian.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: During this period, lapis lazuli beads and other objects are found in a number of burials, which indicates long-distance exchange (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Palettes, in different forms depending on the period, are found in Naqada burials. Maceheads, sometimes decorated, have also been found, as have clay figurines, and ivory combs (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Some human burials are also associated with animal burials. At HK6 in Hierakonpolis, this included an elephant burial (Friedman 2011:39).

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of more exceptional objects found in burials. For information, see Stevenson 2009.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: From this period, there is a huge range in the types and forms of burials. From simple pit burials, to the multi-chambered burials of the elite found at sites such as Abydos and Hierakonpolis.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: I know of no evidence for this from this period.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the burials from this period are found in cemeteries separate from habitation (Stevenson 2009). The most elaborate of these burials, with large superstructures and subsidiary burials of both individuals and animals, are found at Hierakonpolis (Friedman 2011).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: There are occasional group burials, which may belong to a single family, but these are not particularly common (Stevenson 2009).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: Although not common in this period, some burials have been found within settlements, occasionally buried in house floors in large ceramic vessels. Of these, child burials dominate the finds (Stevenson 2009; Brunton and Caton-Thompson 1928:89).

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear how much of the Egyptian pantheon existed in the Predynastic Period, but there are images of supernatural creatures such as a leopard-serpent hybrid, images of bulls that seem to represent the power of the king, or perhaps an early version of Hathor or Bat. Falcon images that are seen as being associated with the god Horus can also be seen. There are very few human-animal hybrids during this period, however, which becomes a significant feature of Egyptian religion in later periods.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Although the evidence for this period is lacking, there does not seem to be a supreme high god at this time, but a collection of deities and a divine king (see further Hendrickx 2011).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Notes: There are clearly deep religious beliefs concerning burials, including a secondary treatment of human remains. Whether at this time, however, the Egyptians believed that human spirits were present and able to affect daily life, is unclear. This becomes a feature of Egyptian religion in later periods.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: It is unclear how much of the Egyptian pantheon existed in the Predynastic Period, but there are images of supernatural creatures such as a leopard-serpent hybrid, images of bulls that seem to represent the power of the king, or perhaps an early version of Hathor or Bat. Falcon images that are seen as being associated with the god Horus can also be seen. There are very few human-animal hybrids during this period, however, which becomes a significant feature of Egyptian religion in later periods.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings take the form of animals. In later periods, a form of indwelling seems to be present, so that falcons, bulls, etc. can serve as vessels for the spirits of gods. The numerous instances of animals in iconography seems to suggest that this is the case in this early period as well.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: Too little evidence to suggest this for this period.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: As the supernatural beings seem to be able to take the form of terrestrial animals, they could be present on earth.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or

the other.

Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In this prehistoric period, there is not enough evidence to say one way or the other.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Although it is difficult to say for certain due to a lack of written sources for this period, much of the iconography seems to be related to ensuring order over chaos. If the ideology connected with these images stays consistent into the following period, then the people, guided by the king, were meant to ensure the gods were happy so that they would keep the peace. This suggests that they could therefore "have deliberate causal efficacy in the world" (see also Hendrickx 2011).

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The iconography suggests that they could ensure that the world is free from chaos, but more detailed information is not available.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The iconography suggests that they could allow chaos to take over, but more detailed information is not available.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Although it is difficult to say for certain due to a lack of written sources for this period, much of the iconography seems to be related to ensuring order over chaos. If the ideology connected with these images stays consistent into the following period, then the people, guided by the king, were meant to ensure the gods were happy so that they would keep the peace. This suggests that they could either directly intervene to ensure peace, or simply allow chaos to takeover by not intervening (see also Hendrickx 2011).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence from this period to answer this question.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence from this period to answer this question.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence from this period to answer this question.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence from this period to answer this question.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: The king comes to be seen as partly divine, but whether the predynastic rulers were viewed this way is too difficult to comment on at this point.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of supernatural beings, this includes so-called "serpopards" and other divine creatures such as falcons and bulls, that later become important deities associated with kingship and power (Hendrickx 2011).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: While in later periods of Egyptian religion many of the gods are organized in a family structure, this does not seem to be present in this early period.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Standards from different areas carry different symbols of gods, suggesting that there are deities associated with specific regions (see Teeter 2011:174).

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While supernatural monitoring in some form is present in later periods, there is too little evidence to suggest this for this period.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the iconography from this period seems to be related in some way to the maintenance of order over chaos (Hendrickx 2011). If this is similar to later periods, then a belief seems to exist that if order is not maintained, and the gods are not kept happy, then chaos will ensue. There is not enough evidence to suggest anything beyond this for this period, however.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: In that the gods help to maintain order.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to give many details on this for this period.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a code of justice and order, referred to as "ma'at" that governs the Egyptian way of life in later periods, but there is too little evidence to suggest whether this was in effect during this early period.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a code of justice and order, referred to as "ma'at" that governs the Egyptian way of life in later periods, but there is too little evidence to suggest whether this was in effect during this early period.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a code of justice and order, referred to as "ma'at" that governs the Egyptian way of life in later periods, but there is too little evidence to suggest whether this was in effect during this early period.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: At least there is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence for this period.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence for this period.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence for this period.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is little evidence.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Although there is little evidence for practices in this period, religious courtyards and areas in places like Hierakonpolis suggest that there was ritual participation by a larger part of the community.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Although there is little evidence for practices in this period, religious courtyards and areas in places like Hierakonpolis suggest that there was ritual participation by a larger part of the community.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: Towards the end of this period, there is significant social differentiation, with individuals that seem to be at least regional leaders with exceptionally wealthy burials (Anđelković 2011).

– A state

Notes: By the end of this period, Egypt seems to have developed a single culture with centralized ruler (Anđelković 2011).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: At the end of this period, a system of bureaucracy seems to exist, suggested by the use of proto-hieroglyphic labels (Anđelković 2011).

– No

Notes: For the vast majority of this period, there is little evidence for the existence of a bureaucracy.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The appearance of Egyptian proto-hieroglyphs and labels with the Dynasty 0 kings names in different regions and sites in the Levant in this period, suggests interactions between different groups.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: While most of the sites in Egypt have no evidence for this in early periods, there are large food storage areas present at Hierakonpolis (Friedman 2011).

– No

Notes: Most sites in this period do not have evidence of this.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence available to answer this question.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: There are images that show Dynasty 0 kings carrying out irrigation works (Scorpion macehead), perhaps as both practical state projects, and to show the maintenance of order.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is very little evidence for this. An image of king scorpion (Scorpion macehead) carrying out irrigation may suggest otherwise, but there is little evidence that this was provided for the general public by the state.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is some suggestion due to the grain and beer storage facilities at Hierakonpolis that there may have been some sort of taxation system in place (Friedman 2011), but otherwise there is too little evidence to be certain.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence of this.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence from this period to answer this question.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In later periods, Egyptian morals and religion are driven by the concept Maat, which means truth, order, and justice. But this is not particularly formal, and there is too little evidence to suggest whether it existed during this early period.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In later periods, Egyptian morals and religion are driven by the concept Maat, which means truth, order, and justice. But this is not particularly formal, and there is too little evidence to suggest whether it existed during this early period.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for this.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is certainly some form of warfare occurring during this period, but whether this included an institutionalized military is unclear.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is certainly some form of warfare occurring during this period, but whether this included an institutionalized military is unclear.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– I don't know

Notes: A form of proto-hieroglyphs are known from this period. They largely take the form of labels at this time. This seems to be mostly related to non-religious, administrative purposes, but they are for grave goods. Also, as religion is difficult to separate from profane throughout Egypt's history, this question is difficult to answer.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A form of proto-hieroglyphs are known from this period. They largely take the form of labels at this time. This seems to be mostly related to non-religious, administrative purposes, but they are for grave goods. Also, as religion is difficult to separate from profane throughout Egypt's history, this question is difficult to answer.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No written evidence for this during this period, though it may have already existed at this time, as it shows up in the written record in the succeeding period.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No written evidence for this during this period, though it may have already existed at this time, as it shows up in the written record in the succeeding period.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Throughout this period, agriculture becomes increasingly important. At the end of the period, there is significant evidence for large scale bread and beer production, and feasting on both wild and raised animals at Hierakonpolis. Much of this seems to be associated with the ceremonial complex (Friedman 2011).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Throughout this period, agriculture becomes increasingly important. At the end of the period, there is significant evidence for large scale bread and beer production, and feasting on both wild and raised animals at Hierakonpolis. Much of this seems to be associated with the ceremonial complex (Friedman 2011).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is too little evidence to answer this question.

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

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